

DIFFUSION SCALING IN EVENT-DRIVEN RANDOM WALKS: AN APPLICATION TO TURBULENCE

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Scaling laws for the diffusion generated by three different random walk models are reviewed. The random walks, defined on a one-dimensional lattice, are driven by renewal intermittent events with non-Poisson statistics and inverse power-law tail in the distribution of the inter-event or waiting times, so that the event sequences are characterized by self-similarity. Intermittency is a ubiquitous phenomenon in many complex systems and the power exponent of the waiting time distribution, denoted as *complexity index*, is a crucial parameter characterizing the system's complexity. It is shown that different scaling exponents emerge from the different random walks, even if the self-similarity, i.e. the complexity index, of the underlying event sequence remains the same. The direct evaluation of the complexity index from the time distribution is affected by the presence of added noise and secondary or spurious events. It is possible to minimize the effect of spurious events by exploiting the scaling relationships of the random walk models. This allows to get a reliable estimation of the complexity index and, at the same time, a confirmation of the renewal assumption. An application to turbulence data is shown to explain the basic ideas of this approach.

Keywords: random walks, renewal processes, power-law, turbulence, self-organization, long-range memory, self-similarity, fractal intermittency.

1. Introduction

Complex systems with many degrees of freedom and strong nonlinear interactions are ubiquitous in nature and in many human activities. In critical phenomena [1]

and self-organized criticality [2, 3], the system typically moves towards a critical point, corresponding to a phase transition from an uncorrelated to a correlated condition. This transition is characterized by means of the critical value of a parameter characterizing the cooperation, i.e. the nonlinear coupling, among many individual units. A complex system at the critical point develops power-law long-range correlation in both time and space and it also displays a typical intermittent behaviour, given by a birth-death process of cooperation. In fact, the dynamical evolution is characterized by the alternance of metastable self-organized states and short-time events marking the transition among two successive metastable states. In self-organized systems, an inverse power-law decay typically emerges in the distribution of inter-event times or Waiting Times (WTs): $\psi(\tau) \sim 1/\tau^\mu$. There are several examples of complex systems displaying power-law behaviour: ecological systems [4], neural dynamics [5, 6], blinking quantum dots [7, 8, 9], social dynamics [10], brain information processing [11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16], atmospheric turbulence [17], earthquakes [18].

In recent years, the measurement of a single molecule tracking in cellular dynamics is allowing the analysis of single trajectories [19]. Many authors found a strong inhomogeneity in the statistical ensemble of trajectories and, thus, a strong evidence of ergodicity violation. Lubelski et al. [20] showed that this ergodicity violation is due to the presence of critical events with slow power-law decay in the WT distribution, a condition sometimes denoted as *fractal intermittency*. In fact, these authors compared time and ensemble averages in a transport model known as Continuous Time Random Walk (CTRW) [21–23], which is based on the presence of critical events in the particle dynamics.

The power-law exponent μ is then a basic parameter measuring, in some sense, the level of complexity of the system, where by complexity we mean the ability of the system to develop self-organized, metastable structures, which can survive for relatively long random times, thus introducing long-range time correlations. These metastable structures affect also the space correlations, as they are usually associated with a coherent motion in the configuration space, such as vortex motion in turbulence. The interpretation of μ is made clear by considering that the limit of large μ is associated with a weak coupling in the nonlinear interactions and, consequently, with a low level of self-organization. On the contrary, as μ decreases, the coupling becomes stronger and the level of self-organization increases. For this reason, μ will be denoted as *complexity index*.

An important feature of critical events in complex systems is often given by a fast decay of the system's memory in correspondence with event occurrence. In this case, a straightforward approach to the description of fractal intermittency is given by the theoretical framework of renewal processes [24]. At variance with other approaches, such as Fractional Brownian Motion (FBM) [25], in renewal modeling critical events, which are assumed to be statistically independent, play a central role and the WT probability distribution $\psi(\tau)$ is the main feature of the model. FBM is more focused on long-range memory, as a memory kernel is explicitly considered in the dynamical equation. In FBM, the memory kernel is the main modeling

ingredient whose inverse power-law tail is related to the long-range auto-correlation function. FBM is a model for anomalous diffusion, thus generalizing the standard Brownian motion for normal diffusion. Similarly, the standard Langevin equation can be generalized to the fractional Langevin equation, where a convolution operator is introduced also in the dissipation term with a memory kernel associated with the noise auto-correlation. It is interesting to note that long-range correlations emerge also in renewal models. In fact, even if the transition events determine a fast drop of system's memory, this same memory remains strong when the considered time lag is entirely included into the time interval between two successive events. In this case, the power-law decay in the correlation is related to the probability of long WTs among two events. Long WTs are rare but, due to the inverse power-law tail in the probability distribution, they occur often enough to determine an inverse power-law tail in the auto-correlation function [13]. Then, at variance with FBM, no explicit memory function is given in the dynamical equation, and the long-range correlation is associated with the fractal time intermittency, i.e. the WT distribution $\psi(\tau)$. Other modeling approaches to complex systems, which were also applied to turbulence and intermittency, are given by nonlinear Fokker–Planck equations [26], superstatistics [27] and multifractality [28].

Regarding renewal approach to intermittency, when dealing with experimental observations the renewal assumption must be verified. Further, the direct estimation of the complexity index from the statistical distribution is not always a reliable approach, as spurious events can be mixed with the genuine critical events. Spurious events have been shown to deeply affect the shape of the time distribution in such a way that the power-law decay could be hidden or unclear, with the apparent emergence of a stretched exponential decay [16]. In some cases, a power-law decay with a power exponent completely different from the real one could also appear, thus leading to misleading results. The presence of spurious events could be associated with added noise in the time series or even with the method used to detect events, due to detection of false positives.

In order to minimize the effect of added noise and spurious events, we propose a method based on the scaling features of diffusion generated by three random walks. The main idea is that the random walks have different walking rules but are driven by the same critical events, that is, by the same underlying intermittent system. When added noise and/or spurious events are mixed with the genuine complex events, different regimes emerge in the diffusion scaling at different time ranges. Consequently, the diffusion method is able to extract the genuine scaling and the complexity of the intermittent system.

In Section 2 we give some definitions and results about renewal processes. In Section 3 the Continuous Time Random Walk (CTRW) model is briefly reviewed. The mathematical tools of CTRW allow to derive analytical results for the scaling exponents of the three random walks, given the assumption of a renewal process with inverse power-law tail in the WT distribution. In Section 4 we give some directions about the possibility of using the random walk approach to estimate not only the diffusion scaling, but also the complexity index and, finally, to evaluate

the renewal assumption. A practical application to turbulence data is shown in order to make clear the basic concepts. Finally, in Section 5 some conclusions are drawn.

2. Renewal processes

A sequence of random events, randomly distributed in time, is described by a *point process*. This is formally defined as a stochastic counting process $N(t)$,

$$N(t) = \int_0^t z(t') dt'; \quad z(t) = \sum_n \delta(t - t_n), \quad (1)$$

where $\delta(\cdot)$ is the Dirac function and $\{t_n\}_{n=0}^{\infty}$ the sequence of event occurrence times. The times t_n are obviously increasing with the index n : $t_{n+1} > t_n$ and $t_0 = 0$ is the occurrence time of the first event. A *renewal process* is a point process with statistically independent events. In a renewal process the WTs, defined by $\tau_n = t_n - t_{n-1}$; $n = 1, 2, \dots$, are mutually independent random variables [24]: $P(\tau_i, \tau_j) = P(\tau_i)P(\tau_j)$, for whatever couple (i, j) . Under this assumption, the occurrence of an event is associated with a dynamical instability determining the basic property of erasing memory of the past. An example is given by the Manneville map [29], displaying long-time “laminar” states with a small Lyapounov exponent and rapid transitions to short-time, quasi-instantaneous, “chaotic” states with a large Lyapounov exponent. This is related to a marginally unstable point, determining a slow “laminar” motion from the unstable point to a chaotic region. Consequently, the times that the system takes to reach the chaotic state are distributed according to an inverse power-law. The chaotic state, displaying a typical bursting behaviour, has low predictability, so that a fast decay of memory occurs within the passage through this state. This short-time state can be seen as a quasi-instantaneous event marking the transition between two statistically independent laminar states. In this sense, the Manneville map represents an important prototype of how an approximate renewal property, power-law behaviour and self-similarity can emerge in a nonlinear dynamical system due to chaotic behaviour. This condition is also denoted as Type-I intermittency, and the scale invariance of the WT distribution allows us to denote with *fractal intermittency* this kind of behaviour.

In the stationary case, a renewal process is uniquely defined by Probability Density Function of WTs (WT-PDF) $\psi(\tau)$. Equivalently, it can be described by the *local rate of event production* $r(t)$, which is the expected number of events per time unit in a neighbourhood of the time t [24]. In the original Cox’s approach [24], $r(t)$ is the rate of failures in an ensemble of independent processes. For example, each process can represent the time evolution of some electronic device, and the breakdown of the device the critical event. In this case, t is the time spent after an initial time $t = 0$ at which all the devices are simultaneously switched on. In the Cox idea, the single process ends and is not replaced by a new one. Then, the rate $r(t)$ at time t is evaluated over the ensemble of “survived” processes (the electronic devices).

At variance with [24], we suppose to have an ensemble of independent stochastic processes $\{\omega\}$, each one described by a sequence of critical events, i.e. by the sequence of occurrence times $\{t_n(\omega)\}_{n=0}^{\infty}$ and by the associated counting process $N(\omega, t)$ given by Eq. (1). Then, the rate of event production $r(t)$ at time t is formally evaluated over the subset of all the processes with an event occurring at some time $t_n < t$. The local rate $r(t)$ is defined as the conditional probability density that an event occurs in an infinitesimal time interval $[t, t + dt]$, given that no events occurred in the time interval $[t_n, t]$

$$r(t) = \lim_{dt \rightarrow 0} \frac{1}{dt} \Pr \{t < t_{n+1} \leq t + dt \mid t_{n+1} > t\}. \quad (2)$$

By using the properties of conditional probabilities, it is possible to prove the following expression for the rate $r(t)$ [24]

$$r(t) = \frac{\psi(t - t_n)}{\Psi(t - t_n)} = -\frac{1}{\Psi(t - t_n)} \frac{d\Psi}{dt}(t - t_n); \quad t_n < t < t_{n+1}, \quad (3)$$

where

$$\Psi(\tau) = \int_{\tau}^{\infty} \psi(s) ds = 1 - \int_0^{\tau} \psi(s) ds \quad (4)$$

is the Survival Probability Function (WT-SPF), i.e. the probability that a WT τ_j , extracted randomly from the ensemble of the WTs $\{\tau_n\}$, is larger than τ . $r(t)$ is an instantaneous rate and, in the time-homogeneous case, it assumes a maximum value at an event, then it decays in time and, then, it is reset at the same maximum value at the next event, and so on. It is then possible to define an average decay rate $g(\tau)$, where τ is the time distance from the preceding event,

$$g(\tau) = \frac{\psi(\tau)}{\Psi(\tau)} = -\frac{1}{\Psi(\tau)} \frac{d\Psi}{dt}(\tau). \quad (5)$$

In the time-homogeneous case, the average rate $g(\tau)$ is the only ingredient needed to define the renewal process. It is worth noting that the renewal condition is given by the independence of $\psi(\tau)$, $\Psi(\tau)$ and, consequently, $g(\tau)$ from the absolute time t , the index n labeling the n -th event and the previous WTs (or, equivalently, the previous occurrence times). This is also seen in Eq. (3), defining the rate in the absolute time t associated with the renewal sequence $\{t_n\}$. In fact, only the explicit $t - t_n$ dependence can be seen, that is, the time elapsed from the last renewal event.

We note that, in this formulation, the external perturbation of a renewal process can be treated through the time modulation of the rate [30]. An explicit dependence on the absolute time t is introduced in the rate $r(t, t - t_n)$, and the point process becomes nonhomogeneous. Interestingly, even if the underlying process is renewal, the perturbation introduces a memory that is not reset by the event occurrence [31], so that a perturbed renewal process becomes a point process with a memory on the WT sequence $P(\tau_n | \tau_{n-1}) \neq \psi(\tau_n)$. A perturbed Poisson process typically displays a nonexponential WT-PDF, such as a stretched exponential decay [32, 33] or even the inverse power-law decay [7, 34, 35]. More surprisingly, for suitable

conditions the response of a non-Poisson process to a harmonic perturbation can be very similar to the response of a Poisson process [36]. This could be of some relevance in the interpretation of some classical experimental results regarding the response of neuro-physiological systems [37–39], which are usually interpreted in the framework of stochastic resonance [40].

Once the rate function $g(\tau)$ is known, the WT-SPF is simply derived by solving Eq. (5) with respect to $\Psi(\tau)$ and imposing the initial condition $\Psi(0) = 1$

$$\Psi(\tau) = \exp\left(-\int_0^\tau g(\tau')d\tau'\right). \quad (6)$$

The WT-SPF of a time-homogeneous Poisson process is an exponential function: $\Psi(\tau) = \exp(-r_0\tau)$; so that, comparing with Eq. (6), it results that the event rate is constant in time: $r(t) = r_0$ [24]. This is in agreement with the well-known property that, in a Poisson process, the mean number of events in a given time interval $[t, t + \Delta t]$ is proportional to the length of the time interval itself: $\langle N[t, t + \Delta t] \rangle = r_0\Delta t$. At variance with Poisson processes, a renewal non-Poisson process is characterized by a non-Poisson distribution of the events, a nonexponential WT distribution and a changing in time event rate $g(t)$. In the following we are interested in power-law behaviour in the WT statistics, as in the case of Manneville map. A simplified stochastic version of the Manneville map has been investigated (see [34] and references therein). This is defined by the dynamical equation

$$\frac{dy}{dt} = \alpha y^z, \quad y \in [0, 1], \quad z \geq 1, \quad a > 0, \quad (7)$$

together with a random injection mechanism:

$$y(t-) = 1 \Rightarrow y(t+) = \eta, \quad (8)$$

where η is a uniform random variable in the interval $[0, 1]$. In the range of parameters compatible with a time-continuous dynamical system, this stochastic model reproduces the basic features of the original Manneville map: the bursting event is given by the passage through the border $y = 1$ and the random injection mechanism mimics transition from the bursting (chaotic) state to the laminar state. The great advantage of the model (7)–(8) is the possibility to derive several analytical results and, among them, an analytical expression for the WT-PDF and WT-SPF:

$$\psi(\tau) = \frac{\mu - 1}{T_0} \left(\frac{T_0}{T_0 + \tau}\right)^\mu, \quad \Psi(\tau) = \left(\frac{T_0}{T_0 + \tau}\right)^{\mu-1}, \quad (9)$$

where

$$\mu = \frac{z}{z-1}, \quad T_0 = \frac{1}{\alpha(z-1)}. \quad (10)$$

Note that both $\psi(\tau)$ and $\Psi(\tau)$ become an inverse power-law, $1/\tau^\mu$ and $1/\tau^{\mu-1}$ respectively, in the long-time range $t \gg T_0$, thus satisfying scale invariance and self-similarity.

Substituting $\Psi(\tau)$ in Eq. (5) or, equivalently, in Eq. (3), it is easy to derive the following expression for the average rate

$$g(\tau) = \frac{r_0}{1 + r_1 \tau}, \quad (11)$$

being

$$T_0 = \frac{1}{r_1}, \quad \mu = 1 + \frac{r_0}{r_1}. \quad (12)$$

In the limit $r_1 \rightarrow 0$, this non-Poisson renewal process reduces to a Poisson one with the rate r_0 . This corresponds to the limit $T_0, \mu \rightarrow \infty$ in Eq. (9), with the constrain $(\mu - 1)/T_0 \rightarrow r_0$. In fact, within this limit, $\Psi(\tau)$ reduces to the exponential function $\exp(-r_0 \tau)$. Note that, in this case, the rate perturbation is obtained through the time modulation of the otherwise constant parameters r_0 and r_1 .

3. Event-driven random walks

Renewal processes are the basic ingredient of transport models described with the Continuous Time Random Walk (CTRW) approach [21–23]. At variance with random walks with fixed time steps, in the CTRW the walker can make random jumps only in correspondence with an event occurrence. The standard random walk is associated with a Markov property of the probability distribution and, then, with a Markovian master equation. On the contrary, the CTRW is non-Markovian and, in particular, is a semi-Markov process [41], defined in the general framework of Markov renewal processes [42]. The generalized master equation is a integro-differential equation of convolution type with an inverse power-law memory kernel in the time axis. Considering the case of discrete jumps over a one-dimensional lattice, homogeneous conditions in both time and space and jumps uncoupled from the WTs, the CTRW master equation is given by

$$\frac{dP(j, t)}{dt} = \int_0^t dt' \Phi(t - t') \sum_{j'} \{p(j - j')P(j', t') - p(j' - j)P(j, t')\}, \quad (13)$$

where the memory kernel Φ is related to the WT-PDF through the expression

$$\bar{\Phi}(u) = \frac{u \bar{\psi}(u)}{1 - \bar{\psi}(u)} \quad (14)$$

and $\bar{\Phi}$ denotes the Laplace transform. Note that in Eqs. (13) and (14) the assumption of an event occurrence at $t = 0$ is also done. Eq. (13) can be easily generalized to nonhomogeneous conditions, n -dimensional lattices and coupled jumps and WTs. This equation can be also generalized to the case when the first event does not occur at $t = 0$, but at some previous time $t = -t_a$, in which case Eqs. (13) and (14) are still valid, but an aged WT distribution must be considered in Eq. (14) [43]. Note that, when a slow power-law decay is seen in the tail of the WT-PDF, i.e. $\psi(\tau) \sim \tau^\mu$, the memory kernel $\Phi(t)$ is also an inverse power-law for long time

lags. From this power-law memory it follows the non-markovianity of the process, as said above. It is important to note that the power-law memory can be considered a long-range memory and determine important consequences only when the decay is slow enough, that is, when the transport becomes non-Gaussian also in the long-time limit. This occurs when $\mu < 2$ or $\mu < 3$ depending on the jump statistics in the CTRW. On the contrary, for $\mu > 3$, the long-time behaviour of the CTRW becomes equivalent to a Markov process with Gaussian distribution, and the time regime of the Markovian approximation becomes larger and larger as μ increases. In the particular case of Poisson events, that is, of exponentially distributed WTs, the non-Markovian master equation (13) reduces to an exact Markovian equation over all times. This is in agreement with the result, given in Section 2, that the Poisson process is the limit, for $T_0, \mu \rightarrow \infty$, of the non-Poisson renewal process described by Eqs. (9) and (11). The asymptotic behaviour of Eq. (13) was derived and rewritten in terms of fractional operators [44, 45, 46, 47], i.e. integro-differential operators generalizing the local derivative of integer order to a nonlocal “derivative” of fractional order [48, 49, 50]. This allows for a unified formalism of generalized diffusion equations with self-similarity different from the Gaussian scaling.

In the following, we briefly review some known analytical results about the scaling exponents of diffusion processes generated by three CTRWs driven by renewal events with inverse power-law tails in the WT-PDF: $\psi(\tau) \sim 1/\tau^\mu$. In the following these events will be denoted as *non-Poisson events*.

The diffusion scaling of the event-driven random walk can be investigated to characterize not only the transport properties, but also the complexity of the system. In fact, when the renewal hypothesis applies, it is possible to guess the complexity index μ , as it will be explained below. The value of μ could be estimated through a direct power-law fit of the WT histogram, but it was shown that, when a difference among the two estimates is found, the diffusion scaling approach is more robust and reliable, since spurious events can affect the WT distribution [16].

Now, we consider three different CTRWs, two of which are dichotomous and the third one has three states. They are driven by the same critical events, and the only distinction lies in the different walking rules [13].

The random walk is defined through a signal $\xi(t)$, which is a kind of random discontinuous velocity, taking two or three different values depending on the event occurrence times. Given a sequence of event occurrence times t_0, t_1, t_2, \dots corresponding to the events 0, 1, 2, \dots , we have the following walking rules:

- (a) Asymmetric Jump (AJ) rule, the walker makes a positive jump ($\xi(t_n) = 1$) in correspondence with each event n , otherwise it stands ($\xi(t) = 0$). In other words, $\xi(t)$ is a sequence of pulses of constant intensity.
- (b) Symmetric Jump (SJ) rule, as in the AJ rule, but the walker can make positive or negative jumps in correspondence with an event: $\xi(t_n) = \pm 1$. The sign \pm is chosen with a coin tossing prescription.
- (c) Symmetric Velocity (SV) rule, the walker moves with constant velocity towards a given direction, in the time interval between two events, then a new random

direction (positive or negative velocity) is chosen in correspondence with an event:

$\xi(t) = \pm 1$; $t_n < t \leq t_{n+1}$. As in the SJ rule, the sign is chosen with a coin tossing prescription.

The diffusion variable of the random walk is derived by simply integrating the signal $\xi(t)$

$$X(t) = X_0 + \int_0^t \xi(t') dt'. \quad (15)$$

Note that the AJ and SV rules are exactly dichotomous random walks, with the states $+1$ or -1 , whereas the SJ rule is a random walk with three states: $+1$, -1 and 0 . Further, in the AJ and SJ rules the diffusion variable $X(t)$ is a piecewise constant function with finite discontinuities in correspondence with the events, and the integral in Eq. (15) can be reduced to a discrete sum. On the contrary, in the SV rule, $X(t)$ is an increasing or decreasing function depending on the sign of the velocity ξ , it is a continuous function, but with discontinuous derivative in correspondence with the events.

The scaling properties of these random walks were extensively investigated in several papers [45, 51–54] by applying the analytical methods of CTRW, i.e. the Montroll-Weiss equation for the Fourier-Laplace transform of the probability density function $P(x, t)dx = \Pr[x < X(t) \leq x + dx]$ [21, 23], or by applying simple scaling relationships in the case of AJ rule [55, 13]. In particular, two scaling indices were found in the asymptotic long-time limit: the self-similarity index δ of the diffusion probability distribution, defined by

$$P(x, t) = \frac{1}{t^\delta} F\left(\frac{x}{t^\delta}\right), \quad (16)$$

and the scaling exponent H of the second moment

$$\sigma^2(t) = \langle (X(t) - \bar{X})^2 \rangle \sim t^{2H}, \quad (17)$$

where \bar{X} is the mean value of $X(t)$. These scaling exponents have been computed in the case of non-Poisson events with the power exponent, or complexity index, μ . The analytical expressions for the diffusion scaling exponents δ and H as a function of the complexity index μ are plotted in Figure 1 and summarized in the following: (AJ)

$$\delta_{AJ}(\mu) = \begin{cases} \mu - 1; & 1 < \mu < 2, \\ 1/(\mu - 1); & 2 \leq \mu < 3, \\ 1/2; & \mu \geq 3, \end{cases} \quad H_{AJ}(\mu) = \begin{cases} \mu/2; & 1 < \mu < 2, \\ 2 - \mu/2; & 2 \leq \mu < 3, \\ 1/2; & \mu \geq 3, \end{cases} \quad (18)$$

(SJ)

$$\delta_{SJ}(\mu) = H_{SJ}(\mu) = \begin{cases} (\mu - 1)/2; & 1 < \mu < 2, \\ 1/2; & \mu \geq 2, \end{cases} \quad (19)$$

Fig. 1. Scaling δ (panel (a)) and H (panel (b)) vs. complexity index μ for the three walking rules: AJ (continuous line), SJ (dotted-dashed line) and SV (dashed line).

(SV)

$$\delta_{SV}(\mu) = \begin{cases} 1; & 1 < \mu < 2, \\ 1/(\mu - 1); & 2 \leq \mu < 3, \\ 1/2; & \mu \geq 3, \end{cases} \quad H_{SV}(\mu) = \begin{cases} 2 - \mu/2; & 1 < \mu < 3, \\ 1/2; & \mu \geq 3. \end{cases} \quad (20)$$

The three rules give a normal scaling $\delta = H = 1/2$ for $\mu \geq 3$, corresponding to the normal (Gaussian) diffusion. This is a consequence of the generalized limit theorem for Lévy stable distribution [56]. For the SJ rule this is true also in the range $2 < \mu \leq 3$, while AJ and SV rules are super-diffusive ($H > 1/2$) in all the interval $1 < \mu < 3$. On the contrary, the SJ rule is sub-diffusive ($H < 1/2$) for $1 < \mu < 2$. Regarding the AJ rule in the range $1 < \mu < 2$, it is interesting to observe that, while being super-diffusive ($H > 1/2$), the scaling δ becomes less than 1/2 for $\mu < 3/2$.

We note that, if the WTs comes from a Poisson process, the values of δ and H are again 1/2 and, in the long-time, we have a Gaussian diffusion. This is not surprising as the Poisson process corresponds to the limit $\mu \rightarrow \infty$.

4. Application to data analysis: the case of turbulence

Assuming the renewal hypothesis, the estimation of the scaling exponents δ and H allows to derive the complexity index μ by inverting the expressions given in Eqs. (18)–(20). This can be done for each walking rule and for both δ and H separately. When the computed values of μ are in agreement with each other, apart from experimental and statistical errors, this analysis not only gives a robust estimation of μ , but also a confirmation of the renewal assumption. For example,

considering the AJ rule, from Eq. (18) we have the following relationships between the scaling exponents:

$$\delta_{AJ}(H_{AJ}) = \begin{cases} 2H_{AJ} - 1; & 1 < \mu < 2, \\ 1/(3 - 2H_{AJ}); & 2 \leq \mu < 3, \\ H_{AJ} = 1/2; & \mu \geq 3, \end{cases} \quad (21)$$

that must be obeyed by the diffusion process when renewal assumption applies.

In [53] it was found that the AJ rule is faster in reaching the scaling regime with respect to the other ones. Considering the finite length of experimental WT sequences, this means that the estimation of μ is usually more accurate in the AJ rule. However, it can be seen from Fig. 1 that both $\delta(\mu)$ and $H(\mu)$ are not invertible functions when $1/2 < \delta < 1$ and $1/2 < H < 1$, as the same value of δ or H corresponds to two distinct values of μ , one smaller and the other greater than 2. Then, the SJ and SV rules can be used to discriminate between $\mu < 2$ and $\mu > 2$. For $\mu < 2$, all the three rules, and the associated values of μ , could be compared to each other. For $\mu > 2$, only SV and AJ rules can be compared. In this range the SJ rule cannot be used to evaluate μ , because it has a normal scaling independently from the value of μ itself. Actually, in the application to real data the usage of the SV rule is limited also by the presence of added noise and, consequently, spurious events. In fact, the SV rule was found to be strongly affected by the insertion of Poisson secondary events, which can be seen as a consequence of added noise in sequences of genuine non-Poisson events [16]. The SV scaling is modified by noise, showing a normal scaling $H = \delta = 1/2$ in the long-time regime, even when $\mu < 3$, and this is due to the added noise in the time series. On the contrary, in the AJ rule the effect of added noise is felt in the short-time range, as the super-diffusive scaling, related to the complex part of the signal, emerges in the long-time regime.

In the following, we show an application of this approach to the estimation of the complexity of a turbulent flow. Firstly, a sequence of events must be extracted from experimental time series. To this goal a set of turbulent velocity data observed in the Atmospheric Boundary Layer (ABL) was considered. The data were collected in a measurement campaign carried out in Lecce (Salentum Peninsula, Apulia region, South-East part of Italy) during March 2004. The instrumental set-up for the measurement 130 of air velocity was an ultrasonic anemometer Gill R3, operating at a sampling frequency of 100Hz, mounted on a horizontal bar placed at the top of a telescopic mast, 9.6m above the ground. The analysis is performed on time series about 8 hours long.

In recent studies on atmospheric turbulence the classical Richardson cascade of turbulent eddies was found to be modified by the presence of large scale coherent turbulent structures emerging from the direct interaction between the turbulent flow and the ground [57, 58]. These coherent structures, which are recognized to play a central role in turbulent transport [59], are generated through short-time bursting

events and can be identified with the self-organized states cited above. The self-organization of coherent structures is maintained for relatively long times, after which a fast decay is observed in correspondence with a new bursting event determining the transition to the successive self-organized state of turbulent motion. Then, the birth-death process of cooperation can be studied through a point process, i.e. a sequence of events. As bursting events are associated with a sudden fluid acceleration, the events are defined as abrupt changes in the moduli of the turbulent velocity increments

$$|\Delta S(t)| = |S(t + \Delta t) - S(t)|, \quad (22)$$

where $S(t)$ is the generic signal at time t and Δt the sampling time of the time series. In our case, the signal $S(t)$ is the turbulent fluctuation, defined in such a way as to minimize the nonstationary effects, which are related to large scale meteorological patterns, mainly affecting the direction and intensity of the mean wind and also turbulent intensity (or energy). A widely used approach in atmospheric studies is given by the linear detrending of the turbulent velocity, evaluated over time windows of 30 minutes [60]. Being also the turbulent energy affected by long-time nonstationary patterns, the detrended velocity components were normalized with the local standard deviation, again computed over time windows of 30 minutes. These detrended and normalized turbulent fluctuations $S(t)$ were then used to define the increments of Eq. (22). The events were defined as the 90th percentile in the statistical distribution of the increments, corresponding to a threshold of about 0.15: $\Delta S(t) > 0.15$. A sequence of occurrence times $\{t_n\}$ was derived in this way and used to define the variable $\xi(t)$ for the three walking rules introduced above. The diffusion variable $X(t)$ was computed by applying Eq. (15) to each walking rule and the scaling exponents δ and H were estimated by using two different tools of time series analysis: the Diffusion entropy (DE) [53] and the Detrended Fluctuation Analysis (DFA) [61], respectively. The DE is based on evaluating the Shannon Entropy of the probability distribution $P(x, t)$,

$$S(t) \equiv - \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} P(x, t) \ln P(x, t) dx. \quad (23)$$

When $P(x, t)$ satisfies the scaling condition (16), it is straightforward to prove that

$$S(t) = \delta \ln t + S_0, \quad (24)$$

so that the scaling δ can be estimated from a best fit. $P(x, t)$ was estimated by considering time windows of duration t in the signal $\xi(t)$, thus obtaining a set of diffusing trajectories $X(t)$ from the integration of $\xi(t)$, over which it is possible to compute the statistical distribution. The DFA is essentially the computation of the second moment $\langle \tilde{X}^2(t) \rangle$ of properly detrended fluctuations. Here we apply a linear detrending over time windows of duration t and the scaling is estimated from a best fit applied to the standard deviation $\sigma(t)$ that, if Eq. (17) applies, obeys the scaling relation

$$\sigma(t) = [\langle \tilde{X}^2(t) \rangle]^{1/2} \sim t^H. \quad (25)$$

Fig. 2. (a) DE and (b) DFA applied to the horizontal component of the turbulent velocity.

Fig. 3. (a) DE and (b) DFA applied to the vertical component of the turbulent velocity.

In Figs. 2 and 3 the functions $S(t)$ and $\sigma(t)$ computed from the DE analysis and the DFA are reported, as functions of time, in lin-log and log-log plots, respectively. Figure 2 refers to the horizontal velocity component, while Fig. 3 to the vertical one. The DE curve of the SV rule shows an asymptotic normal scaling $\delta = 0.5$. The corresponding DFA curve shows a similar tendency in the long-time regime, even if a well-defined scaling $H = 0.5$ does not emerge as the convergence is slow.

The AJ rule also gives a normal scaling, but in the short-time range, which, at variance with SV rule, is more evident in the DFA curve. As anticipated above, the appearance of normal scaling for short times in the AJ rule and for long times in the SV rule is a signature of added noise and spurious Poisson events in the time series [16]. As a consequence, from the SV rule well-defined scaling exponents cannot be estimated. However, it is interesting to note that in the short time regime the DE curve applied to the SV rule seems to have a scaling δ similar to that displayed by the AJ rule, as expected for a renewal process (see

Fig. 1). Even if a reliable estimation of the scaling δ_{SV} cannot be obtained due to added noise, this is a qualitative indication that the scaling δ_{SV} is consistent with the more reliable scaling δ_{AJ} . As seen from Fig. 2 and 3, this is given by $\delta_{AJ} = 0.94$ and $\delta_{AJ} = 0.93$ for horizontal and vertical velocities, respectively. Finally, the DFA curve of the AJ rule displays a well-defined scaling in the long-time regime, given by $H_{AJ} = 0.97$ in both cases. The SJ rule gives a well-defined normal scaling $\delta_{AJ} = H_{AJ} = 0.5$ for both DE and DFA, without any presence of knees, marking the transition among different regimes in the DE and DFA curves. This indicates that $\mu > 2$, otherwise different regimes should emerge in the DE and DFA curve. It is interesting to note that, substituting the value $H_{AJ} = 0.97$ in Eq. (21), it results $\delta_{AJ} = 0.94$, in agreement with the values found directly through the DE analysis, thus giving a quantitative confirmation of the renewal assumption. Then, the value of μ relative to the AJ rule can be computed by inverting Eq. (18):

$$\mu_{AJ}^{DE} = 1 + 1/\delta_{AJ}, \quad \mu_{AJ}^{DFA} = 4 - 2H_{AJ}, \quad (26)$$

which gives $\mu = 2.06$.

5. Concluding remarks

We have reviewed some analytical results about the scaling laws of diffusion generated by three random walks driven by renewal non-Poisson events with inverse power-law tails in the WT-PDF. We have showed that the joint use of the random walks and of the two scaling analyzes (DE and DFA) can be useful in characterizing the complexity of cooperative systems, often displaying self-organized metastable structures, such as the turbulent coherent structures emerging in the dynamics of the atmospheric boundary layer. Complexity is characterized by the complexity index μ and by the renewal condition. In general, the application of the three walking rules should allow to evaluate the renewal assumption and, in the case of self-consistency among the different scaling exponents, to get a robust estimate of μ .

In the case of turbulence data, the application of the event-driven random walks showed a typical limitation of SV rule, which, at variance with SJ and AJ, is greatly affected by the presence of spurious events. However, a qualitative comparison between AJ and SV was still possible, at least in the DE analysis. Further, SJ rule was helpful in discriminating the range of μ ($\mu > 2$ in this case). The complexity index was numerically estimated through the scaling exponents δ and H of the AJ walking rule. The two estimations showed a good agreement that enabled us to claim that the renewal assumption is satisfied with a good approximation and that the value of μ is about 2.06.

Finally, we note that the complexity index μ , characterizing the level of self-organization, can play a central role in the interaction among complex systems. In fact, in recent literature [62, 63, 64] it was found that the response of a complex system to a complex signal depends on the relative values of the perturbing and perturbed complexity indices.

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